

Information Bounds in Determining the 3D Orientation of a Single Emitter or Scatterer using Point-detector-based Division-of-amplitude Polarimetry

Joseph S. Beckwith and Haw Yang^{a)}

Department of Chemistry, Princeton University, Princeton, New Jersey 08544, USA

(Dated: 27 September 2021)

Determining the 3D orientation of a single molecule or particle, encoded in its polar and azimuthal angles, is of interest for a variety of fields, being relevant to a range of questions in elementary chemical reactivity, biomolecular motors and nanorheology. A popular experimental method, known as division-of-amplitude polarimetry, for determining the real-time orientation of a single particle is to split the emitted/scattered light into multiple polarizations and to measure the light intensity using point detectors at these polarizations during a time interval Δt . Here, we derive the Cramér-Rao lower bounds for this method from the perspective of information theory in the cases of utilizing a chromophore or a scattering particle as a 3D orientation probe. Such Cramér-Rao lower bounds are new for using this experimental method to measure the full 3D orientation in both the scattering case, and the fluorescence case. These results show that, for a scatterer, the information content of one photon is 1.16 deg^{-2} in the polar and 58.71 deg^{-2} in the azimuthal angles respectively. For a chromophore, the information content of one photon is 2.54 deg^{-2} in the polar and 80.29 deg^{-2} in the azimuthal angles. In addition, the Cramér-Rao lower bound scales with the square root of the total signal photons. To determine orientation to an uncertainty of one degree requires 7.40×10^4 and 2.34×10^3 photons for the polar and the azimuthal angles, respectively, for fluorescence whereas it takes 1.62×10^5 and 3.20×10^3 photons for scattering. This work provides experimentalists new guidelines by which future experiments can be designed and interpreted.

I. INTRODUCTION

The three-dimensional (3D) orientation of a single particle or molecule is a quantity that can both provide a fascinating insight into the environment around said particle and have an intimate impact on its chemical reactivity. A variety of elementary chemical steps have been suggested to be sensitive to the orientation of one or both of the interacting partners; orientation influences electron/charge transfer via the electronic coupling, one of the factors which modulates such a reaction.¹ Experimentally, this has been shown in multiple contexts—Wu *et al.* showed in a study on electron transfer in ionic liquids that this electronic coupling can vary by an order-of-magnitude upon change of the relative molecular orientation at the same separation between the reactive partners,² to give but one example. Reactive partner orientation has also been shown to influence proton transfer,^{3,4} with Rini *et al.* finding orientational rearrangement of the encounter complex a significant step in the reaction. Reorientation is also a sensitive probe on the local environment—detecting changes in it using bulk⁵ and single particle⁶ techniques has been used to study the local environment inside micelles and in a polymer solution (respectively), to give but two examples of the vast range of environments that orientation may be used to probe. The local environment is also of interest from a chemical reactivity perspective—sensitively measuring the local environment and its effect on chemical reactivity is a longstanding interest in physical chemistry.

If we wish to disentangle the effect of 3D orientation upon chemical reactivity, it is necessary to determine the 3D orientation of a single particle or molecule as fast as possible. This is because it is only by accomplishing this that transient

chemical or physical events that may be relevant to chemical and/or biological function can be fully understood. As a single particle becomes smaller and smaller this becomes more and more demanding—for a $500 \text{ nm} \times 2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ bacterium in water, the time taken to rotationally diffuse by 45° in 3D is $\sim 1.4 \text{ s}$.^{7,8} For a $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ particle (e.g., a virus or a nanoscale drug-delivery vehicle) this time decreases to $\sim 600 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$ and for a single molecule of $\sim 5 \text{ nm}$ diameter it decreases further to $\sim 75 \text{ ns}$. Thus if we wish to probe how the chemical reactivity of a single molecule or a single nanoprobe couples to its orientation—and how both of these couple to function—we will need to be able to determine its orientation on a timescale amenable to resolving its dynamics. One method of determining the 3D orientation of a particle in real-time is to split the emitted/scattered light from a particle into multiple polarizations and to determine the intensities at these polarizations during a time interval Δt .^{9,10} These intensities, or the ratio of them, may then be compared to a numerical or analytical model to determine the 3D orientation. Such an experimental approach is known as division-of-amplitude polarimetry and it has the advantage that many point-detectors (e.g., avalanche photodiode detectors, APDs) can operate with relatively short ($\sim 32 \text{ ns}$ in the case of Perkin-Elmer Single Photon Counting Modules) dead times between photon detection events, conferring a high time resolution to the measurement of 3D orientation. A differing approach involves imaging the emission point-spread-function (PSF) of a single particle and determining the 3D orientation by comparison with a predicted PSF.¹¹ This approach, whilst elegant, is limited in time resolution by the typical 100 Hz frame rate of common cameras which confers a 10 ms time resolution. For example, this approach would render the recording of a $\sim 260 \text{ nm}$ diameter particle's rotational diffusion in water as an apparent 45° “jump” in 10 ms on average. In this example of an ideal case, the underlying dynamics not experimentally recorded can be modeled as “rotational wobble” as seen in some literature. Yet, in

^{a)}Electronic mail: hawyang@princeton.edu

FIG. 1. a) An example of an experimental scheme for measuring the polarization of light from a single particle by scattering using a dark-field condenser. A non-polarizing beamsplitter, Wollaston Prism and polarizing beam splitter are combined to measure the light polarization of the scattered light at four azimuthal angles, shown. It would also be possible to remove the condenser and excite scattering/fluorescence using the same objective used to collect light, with the mirror below replaced with a dichroic mirror and/or other optics to remove excitation light. b) Experimental geometry at the particle. In the case of a scattering experiment, annular light with wavelength λ impinges at an angle $\Theta(\lambda)$, and collected scattered light is bounded by the angle $\Delta(\lambda)$. $\alpha_1(\lambda, S)$, $\alpha_2(\lambda, S)$, and $\alpha_3(\lambda, S)$ are the components of the diagonalized polarizability tensor, and their time-dependent orientation relative to the axes of the laboratory frame— X , Y , and Z —is described by the angles θ and ϕ . The shape and volume of the particle is here simply referred to by S . The dashed lines indicate the projection of α_3 or μ onto the X - Y plane.

complex and potentially dynamically changing environments, the probe’s surroundings are generally not a priori guaranteed to be homogeneous and isotropic which, in turn, raises interesting possibilities. In fact, it is these possibilities which are a major motivation in the current endeavors to experimentally resolve the underlying rotational dynamics. Hence here we focus on a point-detector based division-of-amplitude polarimetry approach to determine 3D orientation and ask the question most relevant to decoupling its effect on chemical reactivity—how many photons are needed to determine 3D orientation to a specified error bound? From this information, and from typical photon fluxes from scattering particles and fluorescent molecules we can answer the further corollary question: how quickly is it possible to meaningfully determine a particle’s 3D orientation?

To answer these fundamental questions for realistic applications, we derive analytical expressions to explore the measurement uncertainties, via the Cramér-Rao lower bound,¹² for measuring the 3D orientation of a single scatterer or photon emitter using a division-of-amplitude polarimeter. A scheme of a such an experiment, and the experimental geometry at the particle, are shown in Fig. 1. These expressions are implemented in the freely available code packages MAT3DOrient and Py3DOrient such that they may be used in the design of experiments. We also use these expressions to explore

the effect on the practical and realizable Cramér-Rao lower bounds of various common experimental factors. Along the same vein, recognizing that the same scientific problem can be studied with either a fluorescent or scattering probe using the same experimental setup, we also include a comparison of these two contrast mechanisms to assist in experimental design planning.

II. BACKGROUND

A variety of experimental implementations exist in the literature to measure the 3D orientation, encoded in the polar angle θ and azimuthal angle ϕ , of a single particle. Based on the information content of each classically detected photon, these can be categorized into PSF-imaging based and point-detection based experiments. For the former modality, the emission (or scattering) PSF pattern of a single molecule or particle is imaged by cameras—a 2D detection modality—where each recorded photon carries the *angular-spatial* information in the emission pattern, possibly with additional polarization information. For the latter modality, the emission or scattering intensities along different polarization light paths are sensed by point detectors—a 0D detection modality—where each recorded photon carries only the *polarization* information. While this contribution focuses on the classical information based on the latter point-detecting division-of-amplitude polarimeter modality for 3D orientation determination, for completeness, below we provide a brief overview of these two categorically different types of experiment performed previously, as well as previous related theoretical work.

On the PSF-based side, a significant first step was Sepiól *et al.* measuring the PSFs from single terylene molecules in 77 K n-alkane films and, by imaging at an axial defocus and comparing to detailed simulations of PSFs, determining the orientation of the two single molecules studied.¹¹ Sick *et al.* expanded on this work by utilizing annular illumination, as this gave much enhanced longitudinal excitation fields, to excite dye molecules near the interface of a room-temperature polymer film,¹³ comparing to detailed simulations of the PSFs expected for annular illumination and finding good agreement between these simulations and experiment. They further suggested that their method could be extended to determining the orientation of dyes far from an interface by taking two images at orthogonal excitation polarizations.¹³ The use of a defocused imaging modality was used by Toprak *et al.* to study the orientation of myosin V near the glass-immersion oil interface.¹⁴ Backlund *et al.* used a combination of a polarizing beam splitter and a spatial-light modulator at $2f$ from the intermediate image plane to simultaneously find the location and orientation of dye molecules embedded in PMMA, showing that only by taking into account orientation could one improve localization precision for super-resolution methods where freely rotating dyes could not be assumed.¹⁵ Backer *et al.* used a combination of modulation of the excitation polarization state and a “wobbling-in-a-cone” model for the molecular orientation to measure the 2D orientation ϕ and degree

of rotational mobility from in-focus single molecules.¹⁶ They then applied this to the measurement of the interaction between DNA and the intercalating dye SYTOX Orange and the nonintercalating dye silicon-rhodamine, finding order relative to the DNA axis for the intercalating dye and no overall molecular order for the nonintercalating dye. Cruz *et al.* used excitation polarization modulation coupled with the use of a polarizing beamsplitter, again using the “wobbling-in-a-cone” model, to image two orthogonal polarizations and link these images to 2D orientation and degree of rotational mobility.¹⁷ They used this to study biological filaments, specifically DNA *in vitro*, microtubules and actin stress fibers. They found that they were able to measure local disorder in these filaments that was unobservable using conventional super-resolution techniques. Most recently Lu *et al.* used the combination of a polarizing beam splitter, an orientation-sensitive phase mask at the back focal plane of the microscope, and the “wobbling-in-a-cone” model to study 3D orientation in lipid membranes.¹⁸ They were able to use the technique to observe lipid composition distributions, their rotational mobility and how these changed after a chemical perturbation.

On the division-of-amplitude polarimeter side, the group of Goldman has explored a variety of methods, including switching light polarization from 0° to 90° (relative to the lab frame) at a regular frequency using a Pockels cell and detecting the emission of a single fluorescent molecule using two APDs after a polarizing beam splitter.¹⁹ They later extended this design such that they were able to switch the illumination light to between 45° and 135° , as well as 0° to 90° .²⁰ Such a design is similar to earlier implementations from Peterman *et al.*,²¹ and from Prummer *et al.*,²² though in both cases they measured the intensities from a single molecule using a single CCD rather than two APDs. The four excitation-polarization division-of-amplitude polarimeter has been used by Lewis *et al.*,²³ as well as Peterman *et al.*,²¹ to study the motion of a variety of cytoskeletal motors. Such an implementation requires the completion of a full excitation cycle before one may estimate the particle orientation; for example, it takes 40 ms for four polarizations as reported in the work of Beausang *et al.*²⁰ A method which requires no cycling of the excitation polarization was put forward by Fourkas,⁹ the proposal being to determine the chromophore orientation using the intensity from at least three of the polarizations of 0° , 45° , 90° , and 135° relative to the lab frame. This implementation has also recently been used by Ohmachi *et al.*,²⁴ in the measurement of myosin V movement and by Lippert *et al.*²⁵ in measuring the molecular motor dynein. A relatively similar implementation was used by Molaei *et al.* in studying gold nanorod rotation in viscous polymer solutions,⁶ with the use of a laser and a scatterer enabling them to measure sub-ms rotational dynamics. Notably however they only measured two polarizations, thus confining the range of observable angles to $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ and $0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 90^\circ$ as opposed to the range of the 4-polarization setup of $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ and $0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 180^\circ$.

It is instructive when thinking about comparing experiments to measure a specific quantity to ask the question: how much information about said quantity can we extract from a specific experiment? Thus from such an information-

based treatment the measurement uncertainty in orientation can be known. For both PSF-based and division-of-amplitude polarimeter-based implementations such a question has been considered before in a number of contexts. For division-of-amplitude polarimeter implementations, Foreman *et al.*²⁶ have considered the information limits of using different idealized experimental schemes to deduce the orientation of fluorescent molecules by imaging the fluorophore’s transverse dipoles. They found a $0.5 \text{ rad}^{-2}/\text{photon}$ information limit to a 2D angle determination. More recently Zhang and Lew have explored the fundamental limits of the PSF-based implementations.^{27–29} They found, using quantum and classical estimation theory, that it is not necessarily possible to design an element for the back focal plane that achieves the lowest uncertainty for measuring all possible rotational motions²⁸ and discussed a number of practical limits in two cases of typical signal-to-background ratio.²⁹ This previous work, whilst elegant and insightful, focused solely on fluorophores and, for the division-of-amplitude polarimetry configuration, only considered the 2D transverse-polarization case.

Alternatively, there are multiple potential advantages to using scatterers—metallic nanorod scatterers have shown excellent biocompatibility,^{30,31} do not photobleach³² and have been shown to give photon flux far in excess of single molecules.³²

These advantageous properties have previously been combined with 2D orientational imaging in order to resolve dynamics that were previously unresolvable via fluorescence; Yasuda *et al.* used laser-illuminated darkfield imaging to observe the 2D rotation of F_1 -ATPase via an attached 40 nm gold nanosphere.³³ Specifically, they attached the nanosphere obliquely to the γ -subunit of F_1 -ATPase and determined the centroid position of the diffraction limited spot of the nanosphere for each frame, finding that a previously-observed 120° rotation step consisted of sub-millisecond $\sim 90^\circ$ and $\sim 30^\circ$ substeps, with these substeps being previously unresolved. This key insight was gained via the combination of the increased photon flux, due to the use of scattering, and use of a high-speed CCD camera. Mazaheri *et al.* combined laser-illuminated darkfield imaging, a division-of-amplitude polarimeter approach, and a high-speed CMOS camera to study the 2D rotational diffusion of $71 \text{ nm} \times 21 \text{ nm}$ gold nanorods on a lipid bilayer.³⁴ With the high photon flux from the nanorod they were able to study rotational dynamics on a lipid bilayer with a time resolution of $2 \mu\text{s}$. Such a high time resolution enabled them to explore the effect of the number of bilayer conjugation sites on the nanorod. For such light-scattering experiments, Yang explained how a 4-detector division-of-amplitude polarimetry setup can be used to infer the 3D orientation of an anisotropic nano scatterer;¹⁰ however, the proposal has yet been realized experimentally nor its measurement uncertainties framed.

Below we sketch the derivation of the Fisher information bounds for determining the 3D orientation of a single light emitter or of a single nanoscale light scatterer. The analytical expressions, with their full forms detailed in the Supplementary Materials (SM), are suitable for the division-of-amplitude configuration that utilizes fixed photon-counting point detectors to afford high time resolution for fast chemical dynamics.

III. THEORY

We will treat two cases: that of fluorophores/luminophores (modelled as transition dipoles with orientation vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$) and nanoscale scatterers with a characteristic polarizability tensor $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. We assume that the dipole approximation is valid—this is generally the case when the particle size is much less than a characteristic linear dimension, $\lambda/(2\pi|\epsilon_m - 1|)$. Here ϵ_m is the complex permittivity of the particle relative to its medium, and λ is the illumination wavelength(s). We also assume that the diagonalized polarizability tensor $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ has three components, $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 \neq \alpha_3$, a reasonable assumption for rods and ellipsoids.^{35,36} The interaction between the chromophore transition dipole and the excitation/collection optics are modeled using the theory derived by Fourkas⁹ and the interaction between the scatterer and the surrounding optics are modeled using the theory derived by Yang *et al.*^{10,37} We will discuss the case of an example experimental setup shown in Fig. 1, where we will measure the scattering/fluorescent signals polarized along the azimuthal axis at at least three of the angles of: 0° (s polarized light), 45° , 90° (p polarized light) and 135° .¹⁰ For clarity, we will recapitulate the essential equations that lead to the signals of interest here.

Unpolarised, annular illumination with wavelength λ and at an angle

$$\Theta(\lambda) = \sin^{-1} \left[\frac{\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}}{n_m(\lambda)} \right]$$

(where NA_{cond} and $n_m(\lambda)$ are the numerical aperture of the condenser and the wavelength-dependent refractive index of the medium, respectively) impinges on a single, scattering particle which we assume to be either translationally stationary or freely moving in space but locked in the optical volume of a microscope.³⁸ The light scattered by the particle is collected over the solid angle bounded by

$$\Delta(\lambda) = \sin^{-1} \left[\frac{\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}}{n_m(\lambda)} \right]$$

where NA_{obj} is the numerical aperture of the collection objective and $n_m(\lambda)$ is the wavelength-dependent refractive index of the medium as before. In both of these equations $n_m(\lambda)$ is assumed to be matched to that of the sample. Both of these solid angles are shown in Fig. 1b. In the case of fluorescence we assume that we do not excite the single particle with a condenser and we only consider the collection objective.

The collection objective and condenser are further described by A , B and C terms (in the case of the collection objective) and an H term (in the case of the condenser) and these are defined, as in Fourkas⁹ as:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{4}\cos\Delta + \frac{1}{12}\cos^3\Delta \\ B &= \frac{1}{8}\cos\Delta - \frac{1}{8}\cos^3\Delta \\ C &= \frac{7}{48} - \frac{1}{16}\cos\Delta - \frac{1}{16}\cos^2\Delta - \frac{1}{48}\cos^3\Delta \end{aligned}$$

with the wavelength-dependence of these terms obviated for readability. The H term is defined as in Yang as:¹⁰

$$H = \cos 2\Theta.$$

These considerably simplify the equations for our detected intensity on our four detectors. For fluorescence, these are⁹

$$\begin{aligned} I_{f,0^\circ}(t, \{\lambda\}, \{w\}) &= I^0 w(A + B\sin^2\theta + C\cos 2\phi \sin^2\theta) \\ I_{f,45^\circ}(t, \{\lambda\}, \{w\}) &= I^0 w(A + B\sin^2\theta + C\sin 2\phi \sin^2\theta) \\ I_{f,90^\circ}(t, \{\lambda\}, \{w\}) &= I^0 w(A + B\sin^2\theta - C\cos 2\phi \sin^2\theta) \\ I_{f,135^\circ}(t, \{\lambda\}, \{w\}) &= I^0 w(A + B\sin^2\theta - C\sin 2\phi \sin^2\theta) \end{aligned}$$

with t referring to time and $\{\lambda\}$ and $\{w\}$ referring to the sequence of N discrete wavelengths $\{\lambda\} = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N\}$ with corresponding relative intensity weights $\{w\} = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N\}$ that make up the fluorescence spectrum. I^0 refers to the incident light intensity. For scattering, these equations are somewhat more complex:¹⁰

$$\begin{aligned} I_{s,0,45,90,135^\circ}(t, \{\lambda\}, \{w\}, S) &= \\ I_0 &\left\{ \sum_i^N [W_{11}^{0,45,90,135^\circ} w |\alpha_1|^2] + \right. \\ &\sum_i^N [W_{13}^{0,45,90,135^\circ} w (\alpha_1 \bar{\alpha}_{3,i} + \bar{\alpha}_1 \alpha_3)] \\ &\left. + \sum_i^N [W_{33}^{0,45,90,135^\circ} w |\alpha_3|^2] \right\}. \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Here t refers to time, S refers to the shape and volume of the particle and thus provides the dependence of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ upon these factors. The $\{\lambda\}$ and $\{w\}$ terms refer to the sequence of N discrete wavelengths $\{\lambda\} = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N\}$ with corresponding relative intensity weights $\{w\} = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N\}$ that make up the illumination spectrum of the light source used to illuminate the scattering particle. The wavelength-specific W functions are described in the supplementary material (Section S1.1).

A. Cramèr-Rao Lower Bound Calculations

If we assume Poisson noise (i.e., photon counting noise) for the scattering or fluorescence experiment, we may calculate the Fisher information¹² matrix elements J_{ij} as³⁹

$$J_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{I_k^\beta T (1 - \beta^{-1})^2}{(1 - \beta^{-1}) \xi_k(\mathbf{q}) + \beta^{-1}} \left(\frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial q_i} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial q_j} \right)$$

in the presence of background, and

$$J_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{I_k^0 T}{\xi_k(\mathbf{q})} \left(\frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial q_i} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial q_j} \right)$$

in its absence.

The parameters are defined as in Watkins and Yang,³⁹ i.e., $\mathbf{q} = \{q_i\}$ are variables of interest (here θ and ϕ) being measured on k independent channels (here 3 or 4). The observed intensity at a detector is written as $I_k^0 \xi(\mathbf{q})$, with I_k^0 a constant intensity at polarization detector k (in a “perfect” experiment assumed to be the same across all detectors) and the dimensionless scaling factor $\xi(\mathbf{q})$ containing all of the \mathbf{q} -dependence of the detected intensity. The detected intensity $I_k^0 \equiv n/(\Delta t)$, where n is the number of photons and Δt is the time taken to observe said number of photons. Across the text n_{tot} will be used to refer to the total number of photons observed across all detectors. T is the averaging time in an orientation-determination measurement. Adding the effects of a detected background intensity I_{bkg} , the total detected intensity is,

$$I(\mathbf{q}) = I_k^0 \xi(\mathbf{q}) + I_{\text{bkg}} \\ = I_k^\beta [(1 - \beta^{-1})\xi(\mathbf{q}) + \beta^{-1}],$$

where

$$\beta = (I_k^0 + I_{\text{bkg}})/I_{\text{bkg}}$$

is the signal-to-background ratio. $I_k^\beta = I_k^0/(1 - \beta^{-1})$.

The Cramér-Rao bound states that the covariance between the estimated parameters q_i and q_j is bounded by the inverse of the information matrix,

$$\sigma_{ij}^2 \geq \left(\frac{\partial \{F(\mathbf{q})\}}{\partial q_i} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \{F(\mathbf{q})\}}{\partial q_j} \right) (\mathbf{J}^{-1})_{ij} \simeq (\mathbf{J}^{-1})_{ij}, \\ \sigma_{ij} \geq \sqrt{(\mathbf{J}^{-1})_{ij}},$$

where this approximation is true when the bias of the estimator $F(\mathbf{q})$ approaches 0, which has been assumed here. As multiple parameters (θ and ϕ) are to be estimated simultaneously, the full information matrix \mathbf{J} must be inverted to find the variances of individual parameters and their covariances. If we are estimating one variable (i.e., θ or ϕ) the standard deviation of that measurement is $\sqrt{(\mathbf{J}^{-1})_{ii}}$.

B. Cramér-Rao bound of θ and ϕ for Scattering

In what follows, we will explicitly discuss the 4-detector setup³⁹ since the 3-detector scheme⁹ can be considered as a special case. We start by simplifying the spectral and α dependent formulae using the following shorthand of

$$\alpha_1(\lambda) = w|\alpha_1|^2,$$

$$\alpha_{13}(\lambda) = w(\alpha_1 \bar{\alpha}_3 + \bar{\alpha}_1 \alpha_3)$$

and

$$\alpha_3(\lambda) = w|\alpha_3|^2$$

where the wavelength dependence will often be obviated for clarity.

We must also normalize our scattering intensity equations such that they are dimensionless—i.e., they, at all θ and ϕ (all \mathbf{q}) simply report the probability of finding a photon at a particular detection channel. We wish to normalise our scattering equation such that, at all θ and ϕ , $I_{s,0^\circ} + I_{s,45^\circ} + I_{s,90^\circ} + I_{s,135^\circ} = I^0$, where I^0 is our total input intensity $I_0^0 + I_{45}^0 + I_{90}^0 + I_{135}^0$. Thus we normalise our intensity functions by dividing by the normalisation factor,

$$\text{NF}_s = \left(2(A+B)(3+H) - \right. \\ \left. (A+3AH+4B(1+H)) \sin^2(\theta) + B(1+3H) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 \\ + B(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta) \sin^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} \\ - \frac{1}{4}(2A+B-B\cos(2\theta))(-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \quad (7)$$

Thus, we have the necessary equations to estimate the lower bound of variance on angular measurements at certain levels of photon flux and signal/background ratio.

Using these equations we may construct the Fisher information matrix \mathbf{J}_s , and thus its inverse \mathbf{T}_s . The Fisher information matrix is constructed as

$$\mathbf{J}_s = \begin{pmatrix} J_{\theta\theta,s} & J_{\theta\phi,s} \\ J_{\phi\theta,s} & J_{\phi\phi,s} \end{pmatrix}$$

and, after summing each element over the appropriate wavelength range of the information matrix (the elements are additive over the range of scattering and thus A, B, C, H and α terms involved in the calculation) the inverse matrix \mathbf{T}_s may be calculated by

$$\mathbf{T}_s = \mathbf{J}_s^{-1} \quad (8)$$

As \mathbf{J}_s is the Fisher information matrix whose elements are $J_{s,ij}$, the Cramér-Rao lower bound for a parameter q is $\sigma(q_i) \equiv T_{s,ii}^{1/2}$, where $T_{s,ii}$ are the elements of \mathbf{T}_s . The elements of \mathbf{J}_s are:

$$J_{\theta\theta,s,\beta} = T \left(\frac{Q_{\theta\theta 1\beta}}{M_{\theta\theta 1\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\theta\theta 2\beta}}{M_{\theta\theta 2\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\theta\theta 3\beta}}{M_{\theta\theta 3\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\theta\theta 4\beta}}{M_{\theta\theta 4\beta}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$J_{\theta\phi,s,\beta} = T \left(\frac{Q_{\theta\phi 1\beta}}{M_{\theta\phi 1\beta}} - \frac{Q_{\theta\phi 2\beta}}{M_{\theta\phi 2\beta}} - \frac{Q_{\theta\phi 3\beta}}{M_{\theta\phi 3\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\theta\phi 4\beta}}{M_{\theta\phi 4\beta}} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$J_{\phi\theta,s,\beta} \equiv J_{\theta\phi,s,\beta} \quad (11)$$

and

$$J_{\phi\phi,s,\beta} = T \left(\frac{Q_{\phi\phi 1\beta}}{M_{\phi\phi 1\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\phi\phi 2\beta}}{M_{\phi\phi 2\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\phi\phi 3\beta}}{M_{\phi\phi 3\beta}} + \frac{Q_{\phi\phi 4\beta}}{M_{\phi\phi 4\beta}} \right) \quad (12)$$

with the Q and M functions shown in the SM, Section S1.2. If we wish to calculate the Fisher information matrix for a 3-detector experiment, we simply omit the 4th terms of equations 9–12. For the case of no background photons, we instead denote the J terms with $J_{\theta\theta,s}$, $J_{\theta\phi,s}$ and $J_{\phi\phi,s}$. The Q and M terms are then replaced by terms shown in the SM, Section S1.3.

C. Cramér-Rao lower bound of θ and ϕ for Fluorescence

It is helpful to compare the Cramér-Rao lower bounds of scattering experiment to those of the equivalent fluorescence/luminescence experiment,⁹ as such a comparison may expand the probe selection amenable to a particular scientific question. Normalizing the intensity terms as before, we find the normalization factor is

$$NF_f = 4(A + B \sin^2 \theta) \quad (13)$$

where the wavelength and spectral weighting have been obviated for clarity, but remembering that for any calculation of the Fisher information matrix the A , B , and C terms must be weighted by w , where w sums across all wavelengths to 1. The Fisher information matrix elements are presented in the SM (Section S1.4). The Fisher information matrix is constructed, as before, as

$$\mathbf{J}_f = \begin{pmatrix} J_{\theta\theta,f} & J_{\theta\phi,f} \\ J_{\phi\theta,f} & J_{\phi\phi,f} \end{pmatrix}$$

and, after summing each element over the appropriate wavelength range of the information matrix (the elements are additive over the range of fluorescence and thus A , B and C terms involved in the calculation) the inverse matrix \mathbf{T}_f may be calculated by

$$\mathbf{T}_f = \mathbf{J}_f^{-1} \quad (14)$$

As \mathbf{J}_f is the Fisher information matrix whose elements are J_{ij} , the Cramér-Rao lower bound for a parameter q is $\sigma(q_i) \equiv T_{ii}^{1/2}$, where T_{ii} are the elements of \mathbf{T}_f .

IV. CALCULATIONS

In utilising equations 8 and 14 practically we must also define a framework for our inputs of α in the case of scattering and w in the case of fluorescence. As an aside, an advantage of the theory derived here is that any method can be used to simulate the polarizability tensor elements. That is, if an experimentalist wishes to question if a novel particle shape or material would be of use in a 3D orientation experiment, this could be simulated numerically and used to answer this question.

Due to its ease of use and its excellent agreement with experiment, for the calculations in this paper we use the analytical theory of Yu *et al.*³⁶ to calculate the polarizability tensor elements for Gold (Au), Silver (Ag) and Copper (Cu) nanorods. For our fluorescence spectra we use the spectra of three fluorescent dyes used in 3D orientation experiments in the past—Rhodamine 6G (Rh6G),^{20,24} Cy3⁴⁰ and 6 nm×26 nm quantum rods (QRs).²⁵ For the QRs, we take the spectra from Deka *et al.*⁴¹ It is noted in passing that QRs are not in fact fluorescent but luminescent, and it is known that their polarization factor depends upon their aspect ratio⁴² in a way that implies the approximation of modeling them as a single transition dipole may not be as accurate as for small fluorophores. On the other hand, this approximation is likely not too extreme in practice in light of their use in previous 3D orientation experiments and the fact that at the aspect ratios used the polarization factor would be anticipated to be extremely high.⁴² All calculations presume the surrounding medium is water, and the refractive index is calculated as in Harvey *et al.*⁴³

In inputting photon count values via the I_k and I_k^β parameters to equations 8 and 14, unless explicitly stated, we use the same value for each detector and report an average n_{tot} . Here, n_{tot} is the expected total number of photons which would be observed from a $\sin\theta$ -weighted average across all θ , with the different values of θ having an intensity calculated using equations 7 or 13. Such a weighting factor is shown in Fig. S6 for a 92 nm×40 nm Au rod and Rh6G as examples. This weighting factor ensures that in an experiment where the particle were freely diffusing the mean total photon numbers observed would be n_{tot} . Where the 3-detector and 4-detector experiment are compared, the signal photon flux I_k^0 and β are the same per detector between experiments, i.e., the overall number of background photons decreases going from a 4-detector experiment to a 3-detector experiment, as do the overall number of signal photons. This is the most reasonable comparison as the common optical elements used in the construction of the division-of-amplitude polarimeter experiment split light to four channels using a combination of two optical elements (e.g., Wollaston prisms,²⁴ polarizing beamsplitters,²⁵ and wire-grid polarizers²⁵). Thus if a 3-detector setup was used it would, in most common implementations, lose signal photons with respect to the four-detector setup.

Spherical coordinates are periodic, thus the θ parameter is only determined as $0 \leq \theta \leq 180^\circ$ and the ϕ parameter as $0 \leq \phi \leq 360^\circ$. In actual fact the range at which we may determine these angles is smaller than that as dipoles exhibit $D_{\infty h}$ rotational symmetry, meaning that we may only uniquely determine them in the range of $0 \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ for θ and $0 \leq \phi \leq 180^\circ$ for ϕ . Thus, any measurement uncertainty above this returned by the analytical formulae is instead converted to the physically meaningful value of 90° for θ and 180° for ϕ . Note well that this is not done for calculations to determine the Cramér-Rao bound or information content of one photon (see Section S2).

Where an averaged Cramér-Rao bound is shown, this average is a $\sin\theta$ -weighted average, $(\sin\theta)\sigma_{ij}$. This quantity represents a physical arc length on the orientation unit sphere

sampled evenly across the surface of the sphere, and thus provides a physically comprehensible average. Except for calculations to determine the Cramér-Rao bound or information content of one photon (see Section S2), all angles (i.e., $0 \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ for θ $0 \leq \phi \leq 180^\circ$) are taken into account in this $\sin \theta$ -weighted average.

Where a Cramér-Rao bound for a scattering experiment was calculated, the illumination lamp was simulated as a Gaussian in λ centered (unless specified otherwise) at the peak of the longitudinal plasmon with a FWHM specified in the text. The number of wavelengths considered (irrespective of the FWHM) was 1000. For the calculation of a Cramér-Rao bound for a fluorescence experiment the collection wavelength(s) were centered at the peak of the emission spectrum and the collection width specified is from filter cut-on to filter cut-off. Again, the number of wavelengths considered irrespective of the filter width was 1000.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is first instructive to examine what signals would be observed as a function of θ and ϕ . This is shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen, the intensity observed at each detector is maximised at the ϕ corresponding to the analyser angle and as θ approaches 0 the contrast between the ϕ angles is lost. We thus may intuitively anticipate that as θ approaches zero our uncertainty in measuring ϕ would be extremely high. The shapes of these signal responses change somewhat dependent on NA_{cond} , NA_{obj} , α and if we are considering a fluorophore or a scatterer, but the similarity is such that the general trends of increased contrast at higher θ and maximised intensity at analyser angle are replicated throughout.

Utilising the theory derived in Section III, we may now answer a number of questions related to measuring the 3D orientation of a single particle that are relevant to the experimentalist. First, we will endeavor to answer the first question we asked in the introduction: how many photons are needed to specify a 3D orientation at a specified precision? We will ask this question whilst showing how different background levels change such an answer. Note that here we use precision as a descriptive qualifier for the inverse of uncertainty, which we quantify using our derived Cramér-Rao lower bounds. Thus a high precision refers to a low uncertainty in our measurement.

A. The Effect of n_{tot} and β on ϕ and θ Uncertainty

We will first discuss the case of the effect of the mean photon flux n_{tot} and the signal-to-background ratio β on the measurement uncertainty. Initially, we will simply see the effect of, at $\beta = \infty$, changing n_{tot} from 10 to 100 and at $n_{\text{tot}} = 100$ changing the β from ∞ to 2. We will discuss the case of an Au rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ illuminated at 671 nm by a $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}} = 1.3$ condenser and with the light collected by a $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}} = 0.7$ objective. These values for the optics are chosen due to being instrumentation recently used to determine particle shape via

FIG. 2. Normalised detector intensities for two of the four polarization detectors as a function of θ , ϕ . Specifically for a) 0° and b) 45° . Light detected is from a scatterer, $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$ and $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$, The scatterer was simulated as a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au nanorod in water illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm .

the spectral contrast fluctuation of gold nanospheres,³⁷ a related problem. The effect of both n_{tot} and β on the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and θ is shown in Fig. 3. Comparing the upper four panels, we unsurprisingly observe that the higher number of photons leads to a lower measurement uncertainty in both θ and ϕ . It is also clear that for scattering the measurement uncertainty in ϕ is considerably lower to that in θ , which has (for the 10 photon case) large areas where the highest measurement uncertainty of 90° occurs. This can be understood in the context of Fig. 2: as θ approaches 90° , at any ϕ the detector intensity virtually does not change as θ changes. This is due to the fact that $\theta = 90^\circ$ is a point of orientation degeneracy when using a 4-detector division-of-amplitude polarimeter: the observed intensities on the 4 detectors will be identical for a scatterer with $\theta = 90^\circ + \alpha$ vs. $\theta = 90^\circ - \alpha$ for

FIG. 3. How the n_{tot} and β affects the measurement uncertainty in a) ϕ and b) θ vs. θ and ϕ . The scatterer was simulated as a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au nanorod illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm . Open circles indicate the regions at which the Cramér-Rao lower bound is undefined. Thick lines show where the Cramér-Rao lower bound equals 180° or 90° for a) and b) respectively. Insets show data at $\phi = 90^\circ$ scaled by a factor of $(\sin \theta)^{1/\sigma}$, showing the uncertainty in measuring a physical arc length. Dots show where underlying Cramér-Rao lower bound equals 180° or 90° . As the data are periodic, we do not show the full surfaces scaled.

FIG. 4. Data from upper four panels of Fig. 3, $n_{\text{tot}}=10$, $\beta = \infty$. $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ vs ϕ at $\theta = 45^\circ$ (top) and $\sigma_{\phi\phi}$ vs ϕ at $\theta = 90^\circ$ (bottom). Dotted lines are $\phi = 45, 90$ and 135° .

any α value. Similar to the poor localization precision in the axial direction of a standard epifluorescence microscope near the focus,⁴⁴ this symmetry leads to increasing uncertainty as $\theta \rightarrow 90^\circ$. Thus we have an area where we must have very high photon counts to distinguish nearby θ values, not possible at low n_{tot} .

Comparing the lower four panels, we may observe the effect of β on the measurement uncertainty for two cases of $\beta = \infty$ and $\beta = 2$. As is again unsurprising, the addition of a significant amount of background noise in going from $\beta = \infty$ to 2 increases the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and θ . Again, we see a lower measurement uncertainty in ϕ than θ in these cases. It is notable that the measurement uncertainty is not hugely affected by β —a change from ∞ to 2 is the addition of a substantial background noise but the measurement uncertainty does not become so large that we will be totally unable to determine the probe's orientation. Indeed, the calculations suggest we will still be able to precisely measure a substantial number of orientations. This is positive, suggesting these experiments do not require an unreasonable amount of effort to produce reasonable results.

The oscillations in the ϕ and θ measurement uncertainties in the case of no background are shown more clearly in Fig.

4 at a single θ value. This shows that the oscillations appear to be 45° out-of-phase with one another, with the ϕ measurement uncertainty being lowest when the ϕ is between two detector analyser values and the θ being best at a detector analyser value. This again can be understood in reference to Fig. 2—when the ϕ is at an analyser angle, we have two detectors for which the intensity changes very little as a function of ϕ in the vicinity, increasing the measurement uncertainty in ϕ . By contrast, for the measurement of θ having two detectors with a large contrast gives us an advantage in our measurement. This is due to the fact that we observe more of a change in intensity as we change θ at these ϕ values, thus we have more information. In the case of going from $\beta = \infty$ to $\beta = 2$, this smooths out the oscillations observed in the case with no background. The smoothing out of the oscillations can be understood by considering that with the addition of a large amount of background noise, detecting small changes in intensity would prove difficult.

FIG. 5. How n_{tot} and β affect the measurement uncertainty in a) ϕ and b) θ . The scatterer was simulated as a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au nanorod illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm .

The effect of both n_{tot} and β on the measurement uncertainty of ϕ and θ is shown for a range of both parameters

in Fig. 5, with each data point representing a $\sin \theta$ -weighted mean (i.e., a free diffusion weighted mean) of the full θ , ϕ surfaces shown in Fig. 3. The measurement uncertainty appears to be considerably more affected by n_{tot} than β , and again with the optics and scatterer considered here we observe a higher measurement uncertainty in θ than in ϕ . Thus we have used the theory presented in Section III to answer our first question posed in the introduction: what is the number of photons needed at different β levels to determine 3D orientation to a specified precision. We may also ask corollary questions: does our measurement uncertainty tend to 0 as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$? Fig. 6a, as well as the derivation in Section S2, show this to be the case. Furthermore, does our measurement uncertainty decrease proportionally to $n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$, similar to the increase of localization precision of Gaussian profiles in super-resolution microscopy?⁴⁵ Fig. 6b shows this to also clearly be the case. The prefactors (p_c s) for fits to the measurement uncertainty at different β levels enable us to state clearly the information carried by a single photon. We derive the information carried by a single photon by the simple calculation p_c^{-2} (where p_c is in radians). In the case of $\beta = \infty$ the information content is 58.71 deg^{-2} in ϕ and 1.16 deg^{-2} in θ . Such a result puts a quantitative number on the earlier discussion that our measurement uncertainty in θ is considerably higher than in ϕ , due to the nearly two orders-of-magnitude lower information content in a single photon. Put another way, the Cramér-Rao bound for one detected photon is 56.6° in ϕ and 402° in θ —a considerably higher uncertainty in θ than in ϕ . The prefactors for the fits to the measurement uncertainty are shown in Tables S1–S4 and enable a rapid computation of the expected measurement uncertainty at different photon flux and β levels.

B. Effect of the Experimental Instrumentation

It seems natural that given that these results are specific to one set of NA_{cond} and NA_{obj} values, albeit one that has been shown to be experimentally useful,³⁷ to ask the question of how the NA_{cond} and NA_{obj} values affect the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and θ . This is shown (for $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$ and $\beta = 100$) in Fig. 7. As can clearly be seen, the effect of changing the NAs of the condenser and the objective do not cause equal changes to the measurement uncertainties of ϕ and θ . In particular, increasing the condenser NA causes an increase in the precision of ϕ but a decrease in the precision of θ at low NA_{obj} . Maximizing both condenser and objective NA achieves higher precision in θ and leads to a small, 1.4° in this case, degradation of the ϕ precision. By contrast, lowering the objective NA leads to a, considerably larger, 24° decrease in θ precision. This suggests that for a scattering experiment the trade-off is clear and maximizing the NAs of the optics used is the best strategy for minimizing uncertainty.

In what precedes we have assumed that we illuminate with a single wavelength (e.g., with a laser) and that this wavelength coincides with the peak of the longitudinal plasmon resonance. It is thus of interest to examine how the illumination wavelength affects the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and

FIG. 6. a) How the uncertainty in θ (upper panel) and ϕ (lower panel) changes as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$. $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and the scatterer was simulated as a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au rod, illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm. b) Fits to $\beta = \infty$ data using a model of $p_c \cdot n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$, where p_c is a proportionality constant.

θ , as experimentally it may not always be possible to illuminate at the longitudinal plasmon resonance peak. In the case of a changing illumination wavelength for a scatterer the change of wavelength will enter into equation 8 via the wavelength-dependence of α , which may produce a pronounced difference in measurement uncertainties. This is indeed the case, shown in Fig. 8.

Clearly for a scatterer the choice of illumination wavelength will lead to a significant change in the measurement uncertainty of ϕ and θ in a way that is not the same for either angle. For θ , Fig. 8a, the uncertainty is lowest near the scattering peak of the transverse plasmon (here 532 nm) and is highest at the blue edge of the longitudinal plasmon. Such behavior appears to correlate relatively well with the magnitude of the cross-term α_{13} . Where this term is most negative, the measurement uncertainty in θ is highest. Conversely, as it tends to 0 the measurement uncertainty in θ is lowest.

For ϕ , Fig. 8b, the picture is almost opposed—the area where the measurement uncertainty is lowest is close to the scattering peak of the longitudinal plasmon (here 671 nm). This measurement uncertainty increases significantly as the illumination wavelength shifts to the blue, with light frequency at the transverse resonance causing the measurement uncertainty to change by an order-of-magnitude from 1.6° to 22.5° . Such a change appears to correlate reasonably well with the magnitude of the α_1 term, with the measurement uncertainty increasing as this term increases in magnitude.

Thus one must explicitly take into account the wavelength dependence of α in both planning and analysis of 3D orientation experiments, as a change of illumination wavelength can have a significant impact on the measurement uncertainties in θ and ϕ .

The fact that the measurement uncertainties in θ and ϕ for a scatterer change dependent on the illumination wavelength suggests that illuminating with a range of different

wavelengths, as would be typical for a lamp, will also have an effect on these measurement uncertainties. Their change as we change our illumination width is shown in Fig. 9.

As we increase the spectral width of the lamp that we illuminate our particle with, the measurement uncertainties for both angles change quite differently. For ϕ , as we increase our range of illuminated wavelengths from 1–200 nm our measurement uncertainty increases by a factor of ~ 1.8 at all n_{tot} values. By contrast, the measurement uncertainty of θ is not amplified by increasing the lamp width—after a rise going from 1 nm to ~ 50 nm the measurement uncertainty drops dramatically. This can be understood in the context of Fig. 8. As we increase our lamp width, we begin collecting scattered photons from the region around the transverse plasmon where our measurement uncertainty is much less relative to simply illuminating the longitudinal plasmon. The factor by which the θ measurement uncertainty drops is 1.25 at $n_{\text{tot}} = 10$ and 2.6 at $n_{\text{tot}} = 3000$. Thus dependent on the photon flux it would seem that increasing the range of illumination wavelengths may yield a lower uncertainty at high flux, or a higher one at low flux. It should also be noted that in a real experiment increasing the range of collected wavelengths, if one is illuminating with a lamp, most likely increases the photon flux and so there is a trade-off between how the measurement uncertainties will change due to the range of illumination wavelengths collected and the achievable flux. In the example of the $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au nanorod it would seem clear that increasing the range of detected wavelengths would be beneficial due to the improvement in θ precision and photon flux, assuming that this does not lower the β by a large factor.

In what precedes, we have discussed measurement uncertainties for the case in which we measure the scattered photons at all four polarization angle detectors and assuming all of these detectors are aligned such that the intensity at them is equally balanced. However, it has been suggested by authors

FIG. 7. How uncertainty in a) ϕ and b) θ changes with NA_{cond} and NA_{obj} . $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$, $\beta = 100$. σ_{ij} is shown relative to the lowest value for the optics considered here. The scatterer was simulated as a $92\text{ nm} \times 40\text{ nm}$ Au nanorod illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm.

in the past⁹ that it would be possible to use only 3 detectors to measure the full 3D orientation of a single particle. Further, experimental implementations to measure 3D orientation almost always apply multiplicative factors to the measured photon counts to correct for detector imbalances that arise from imperfect beamsplitters etc.^{24,25} These thus beg the questions of how do our precision limits for a 3-detector and a 4-detector experiment (assuming equal numbers of photons per detector) compare, and how does more/less photon flux on one detector vs. the others affect the measurement uncertainties?

In the case of the number of detectors, it is clear from an information theory perspective that 4 detectors must, in the case of shot-noise limited detection, always outperform 3—a 4th detector is more information and thus axiomatically we must gain precision from that. Furthermore, in realistic conditions of the same number of signal photons and background photons per detector, 4 detectors always outperform 3 at a range

FIG. 8. The effect of illuminating at different wavelengths on a) θ and b) ϕ uncertainty. The scatterer was simulated as a $92\text{ nm} \times 40\text{ nm}$ Au nanorod (scattering spectrum shown as dashed line) with illumination of 1 nm FWHM centred at a particular illumination wavelength. These uncertainty values are compared with the polarizability tensor elements α_1 and the cross-term α_{13} . $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$, $\beta = 100$.

FIG. 9. The effect of changing the lamp illumination width on measurement uncertainties of a) ϕ and b) θ . The scatterer was simulated as a $92\text{ nm} \times 40\text{ nm}$ Au nanorod, width $NA_{\text{cond}} = 1.3$ and $NA_{\text{obj}} = 0.7$. $\beta = 100$. Lamp is centered at 671 nm.

of n_{tot} and β . This is shown in Fig. S4. Given virtually all experimental implementations of the experiment have used four detectors (we could not find an example of only 3 detectors being used) this is something that clearly the community has already realized.

For the case of detector misalignment, we plot how changing the weight of intensity on the k th detector affects the measurement uncertainty with respect to the best case (detectors equally balanced). As the weight of intensity on the k th detec-

tor is changed the intensity on the other N detectors is changed as

$$I_{\text{detector} \neq k} = \frac{N - \text{weight}}{N - 1}$$

though in an actual experiment how the intensities are weighted on each detector may be more complex than this.²⁵ These data are shown for all four detectors in Fig. 10.

FIG. 10. Effect of changing the weight of intensity at detector k on measurement uncertainty in a) θ and b) ϕ . $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and scatterer was simulated as an Au rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$. $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$, $\beta = 100$. Rods illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm . Inset shows a zoom of the 0° detector Cramér-Rao lower bound change around the 0.5 – 1.5 weight region.

As can be seen detector imbalance can increase the measurement uncertainty significantly, though this only appears to be the case at extreme changes of the weights. It appears to make no difference which detector has an intensity weight change on the *average* measurement uncertainty, as we would expect. The change to $(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\phi\phi}$ and $(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\theta\theta}$ as a function of ϕ is different depending upon which detector has an intensity weight change, shown in Figures S2 and S3 respectively. $(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\phi\phi}$ has a minor decrease in measurement uncertainty around where ϕ equals the detector angle (or is 90° away) as the intensity weight is decreased on that detector and a decrease around where ϕ is $\pm 45^\circ$ from the detector angle. By contrast, there is an increase in measurement uncertainty around where ϕ equals the detector angle as the intensity weight is increased on that detector and a decrease in measurement uncertainty in ϕ around where ϕ is $\pm 45^\circ$ from the detector angle. $(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\theta\theta}$ behaves slightly differently—this has a minor decrease in measurement uncertainty around where ϕ equals the detector angle, as well as $\pm 45^\circ$ away, as the intensity weight is decreased on that detector and a significant increase in measurement uncertainty around where ϕ is 90° from the detector angle. There is a decrease in measurement uncertainty around where ϕ is 90° away from the detector angle as the intensity weight is increased on that

detector and an increase in measurement uncertainty in ϕ around where ϕ is the detector angle, or is $\pm 45^\circ$ from the detector angle.

In cases of detector weight closer to the ideal the average effect is not particularly drastic, with halving/doubling the intensity on one detector relative to the others only bringing about $\sim 2\%$ increase in measurement uncertainty (inset of Fig. 10). Where the data is shown the experimental implementations of the technique are well within such a region²⁵ so it can be anticipated that the increase in measurement uncertainty due to this in real experiments is minimal. These results have all been for a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au rod. However, the results of Figs. 8 and 9 imply that the measurement uncertainties in θ and ϕ will be dependent on the illumination wavelengths via the polarizability tensor α , which changes with scattering material and rod dimensions. Thus this begs the question of how will the measurement uncertainty change with scattering material.

C. Photon Source

For scattering we compare the three rod elemental compositions of Au, Ag, and Cu, with each longitudinal plasmon resonance centered at 671 nm . This corresponds to an Au rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$, an Ag rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 30.5 \text{ nm}$ and a Cu rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40.25 \text{ nm}$. The measurement uncertainties are shown in Fig. 11 for a range of n_{tot} in the case of no background. At all intensities the Ag rod is shown to have the lowest measurement uncertainty in θ and ϕ , followed by the Au then the Cu rod. This tracks the spectral separation of the longitudinal and transverse plasmon resonances—highest for Ag, lowest for Cu (Fig. S10).

FIG. 11. The effect of scattering material on measurement uncertainty for θ (top) and ϕ (bottom) as a function of photon flux. $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and scatterers were simulated as an Au rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$, an Ag rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 30.5 \text{ nm}$ and a Cu rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40.25 \text{ nm}$. Illumination source set as a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm .

The result of changing scattering material implies that the measurement uncertainty will also depend on the aspect ratio R , where R is Length/Width, of the scattering particle. We indeed find this to be the case (Fig. S11), with the trend being that higher R leads to lower measurement uncertainty in both θ and ϕ . There is however considerable scatter in such a trend, with the CRLB in these calculations varying with particle length and width at constant R . This is explained by the changing spectral separation of the longitudinal and transverse plasmon resonances dependent on different lengths and widths. We may observe a clear quasi-linear trend in increases of the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and in θ as the relative weight of the α_1 term present at the scattering wavelength increases (Fig. 12). This highlights that for optimal performance in measuring 3D orientation one must utilise a probe where the length and width are optimized such that the longitudinal and transverse plasmons are well separated.

FIG. 12. The effect separation of the longitudinal and transverse plasmon resonances (shown by the relative magnitude of the α_1 term) on a) the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and b) the measurement uncertainty in θ for 3 different metal rods. Here $n_{\text{tot}}=1000$, $\beta=100$. Rods illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at the peak longitudinal plasmon resonance wavelength.

In Fig. 12, the effect on the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and in θ was small in both cases, with the transverse and longitudinal plasmons separated sufficiently such that the relative weight of α_1 was at max $\sim 4.5\%$. This is in part due to the fact that our minimum R considered was 2, as below this the approximations underpinning the theory by Yu *et al.* break down (see Fig. S12 for an example). As such we performed additional calculations using Gans theory^{35,46} to simulate the spectral response of prolate ellipsoids of changing shape factor ξ and how this changing spectral response propagates to the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and in θ . ξ is defined as r_L/r_S , where r_L is the semimajor axis and r_S the semiminor axis. As $\xi \rightarrow 0$ the particle tends to a spherical shape and hence $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3$. As this occurs we would anticipate the particle has no privileged direction and thus its 3D orientation to become unknowable as all orientations become equivalent. This

is indeed what we find (Fig. S13) and this is again explained by increasing contributions from α_1 at the scattering wavelength (Fig. 13). Here the trend tends away from linearity above $\sim 20\%$ contribution of α_1 as above this there is extreme overlap between the “transverse” and “longitudinal” plasmons as essentially any distinguishing between them disappears.

FIG. 13. The effect separation of the longitudinal and transverse plasmon resonances (shown by the relative magnitude of the α_1 term) on a) the measurement uncertainty in ϕ and b) the measurement uncertainty in θ for 3 different metal prolate ellipsoids. Here $n_{\text{tot}}=1000$, $\beta=100$. Ellipsoids illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at the peak longitudinal plasmon resonance wavelength.

These results imply that the effect of changing the spectral width of the illumination source will also change depending on the location of the longitudinal and transverse plasmons relative to one another. This thus implies that the range of collected photons should be tuned by adding filters on a sample-to-sample basis.

These results have all been for single particle scattering, as such an experiment confers a number of advantages. As discussed earlier, metallic nanorod scatterers do not photobleach³² and have shown excellent biocompatibility.^{30,31} In addition, with the correct choice of scatterer and illumination wavelength the rate of photons collected from a single scatterer can be significantly higher than from a single molecule.³² Nevertheless it is certainly the case that the contrast achievable by using an anisotropic scatterer may lead to a lower polarization contrast than by using a single fluorophore. This fact, and the fact that fluorescence is widely used to measure 3D orientation,⁴⁷ lead to the question of how comparable are the measurement uncertainties in ϕ and θ for a fluorescence and scattering probe, particularly when one is considering using either to study the same physical phenomena.

The differences between measurement uncertainties of a fluorophore and a scattering particle are shown in Fig. 14. The optics are simulated as identical, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and for the scattering case $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$. At all n_{tot} , β values the measurement uncertainty in ϕ for the fluorophore is less than for

FIG. 14. Difference in increase in measurement uncertainties in a) ϕ and b) θ between a fluorophore and a scattering particle. The scatterer was simulated as a $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$ Au nanorod illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm . The fluorophore was simulated as a Rh6G molecule and the fluorescence filter width was 1 nm at 547 nm .

the scatterer (Fig. 14a), though by relatively small values of $<1^\circ$. The measurement uncertainty in θ is slightly different—at low n_{tot} , β the scatterer outperforms the fluorophore, but as the n_{tot} and β increase the same trend as for ϕ is observed and we see that the measurement uncertainty of the fluorophore is lower than the scatterer by up to $\sim 4^\circ$. Such results would seem to suggest that, in principle, it is always advantageous to use a fluorophore to determine 3D orientation. Indeed the information content of a single photon would tend to back up this claim— 2.54 deg^{-2} for θ and 80.29 deg^{-2} for ϕ , more information than the scattering experiment. Equivalently, the Cramér-Rao lower bound for a fluorophore using a single photon is 272° for θ and 48.4° for ϕ , lower than the scattering case. This is shown in Fig. S1.

It is not necessarily the case that fluorescence is “always” the better choice, however. There is also a question of for how long it is possible to follow the dynamics of a single particle

and at what timescales one may observe dynamics at typical photon flux levels. At high laser power, Sturzenegger *et al.* recently were able to achieve a photon flux of ~ 200 photons/ms from single fluorophores in studying transition path times,⁴⁸ however, these molecules bleached rapidly in $<1 \text{ s}$. A more typical flux is 25 photons/ms.⁴⁹ Though in principle both fluorescence and scattering are background-free techniques, in practical implementations dark counts, readout noise and other sources will always lead to background being present. Moerner and Fromm give a “practical” achievable β of $3\text{--}10$ for single-molecule fluorescence experiments,⁵⁰ and experiments in our laboratory using a lamp-based illumination scheme to study Au nanorods have given a β of 21 ± 8 for scattering. Thus on the timescale of milliseconds the measurement uncertainty in a fluorescence experiment will likely be high—even assuming a β of 10 (the high end of the expected range) one would have to sum over 40 ms to achieve a measurement uncertainty of 1.8° in ϕ and 14.2° in θ . Such a calculation assumes an NA_{obj} of 0.7 and single-wavelength collection, to be directly comparable to the scattering case. 40 ms is roughly the time taken for a $\sim 400 \text{ nm}$ diameter particle to rotationally diffuse 45° . As such, in response to the question posed in the introduction of ‘how quickly is it possible to meaningfully determine a particle’s 3D orientation’ it would seem using fluorescence that, if we wish to study dynamics of a virus or protein complex, the answer is ‘not quickly enough’! It is however possible to improve the photon flux by using luminescent quantum rods, with Lippert *et al.* reporting ~ 600 photons/ms²⁵ (though an unknown β). This would yield, assuming again a β of 10 , the same measurement uncertainty as using a single fluorophore in only 1.6 ms . This time is roughly the time taken for a $\sim 135 \text{ nm}$ particle to diffuse 45° , considerably widening the range of objects where we may study their 3D orientation with sufficient time resolution. Quantum rods also have an advantage in that they bleach considerably slower than single fluorophores⁴¹ though they do blink.⁵¹ For scattering, experiments in our laboratory using a lamp-based illumination scheme to study Au nanorods have yielded a photon flux of ~ 900 photons/ms and a β of 21 , giving measurement uncertainties of 1.8° in ϕ and 14.3° in θ . Such a measurement uncertainty is comparable to the fluorescence case at a higher time resolution, and would enable the study of $\sim 120 \text{ nm}$ diameter particles. It should of course be noted here that all of these speculative calculations about which particles are suitable for study using fluorescence and scattering assumed the medium as water—if a more viscous medium is used, each experimental modality is able to study correspondingly smaller particles. Here, the calculation assumes an NA_{obj} of 0.7 , an NA_{cond} of 1.3 and single-wavelength collection. Where slower dynamics are expected and thus integration times may be longer luminescence may be superior to scattering in following 3D orientation, as per photon more information is conveyed. Conversely, scattering enables a higher time-resolution look into rotational dynamics and thus would seem more suited for faster dynamics. In addition, as previously discussed metallic nanoparticles do not photobleach nor do they blink.³² This would enable the observation of dynamics over considerably longer timescales

than for luminescence, with Yguerabide & Yguerabide finding a constant, to within 2%,³² intensity from a scattering gold nanoparticle over a number of hours. As with many experiments, the choice between luminescence and scattering is problem dependent, and the measurement uncertainties derived here may provide additional information in that choice.

It is also of interest to consider the questions asked in relation to instrumentation of using fluorescence as opposed to scattered light. Thus, as in section V A, the dependence of measurement uncertainty in θ and ϕ on NA_{obj} was calculated (Fig. S7). The fluorescence case is similar to the scattering case, with changing the NA_{obj} having a much larger effect on the θ measurement uncertainty than on that of ϕ —with a mere 2° change in the ϕ measurement uncertainty as the θ measurement uncertainty changes by $\sim 50^\circ$. Again, the strategy to minimize measurement uncertainty would appear to be to maximize the NA_{obj} .

We may also question how the collection wavelength will effect the measurement uncertainty for fluorescence. In this case as the only wavelength-dependence that enters into equation 14 is in the A , B and C terms. We may thus anticipate that changing the collection wavelength or changing the range of collected wavelengths will have very little effect on the achievable measurement uncertainty, as the change of these terms with wavelength is minor. It is indeed the case that the measurement uncertainty is virtually unchanged with collection wavelength (Fig. S8), the range of collected wavelengths (Fig. S9) or the chromophore (Fig. S14). This is excellent news from the perspective of an experimentalist—one may simply optimize the filter width and chromophore from the perspective of achieving the highest photon flux and β without worrying about the effect on measurement uncertainty in θ and ϕ .

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have investigated the fundamental limits for precisely determining the three-dimensional (3D) orientation of a fluorescent or luminescent photon emitter, as well as those of determining the 3D orientation of a nanoscale anisotropic scatterer. We derived this new information theory framework based on an experimental scheme of a division-of-amplitude polarimeter with fixed photon-counting point detectors. This is justified as this configuration potentially enables the resolution of dynamics that are too fast for currently available experimental methods. Thus, this work contributes an information-theoretic bound of observing one aspect of complex chemical dynamics.

The formal theoretical results of Eqs. 8 and 14 depend upon the explicit analytical expressions found in the Supplementary Material, Eqs. S13–S59 and Eqs. S60–S65 respectively. These analytical results show that photons are the most fundamental information carrier in division-of-amplitude polarimetry experiments, as expected, and that the Fisher information is proportional to the total number of photons in such an experiment. Fig. 11 displays a key result of this work, showing the measurement uncertainty of determining a chromophore

or nanoscale scatterer’s 3D orientation depends on the scattering material and the number of detected photons. In practical applications, for example, this figure can serve as a reference for assessing the execution of a particular experiment or the performance of an instrument. We were also able to determine the Cramér-Rao lower bound for measuring θ and ϕ using a single photon for both the scattering case (Fig. 6) and the fluorescence case (Fig. S1), and thus also clearly state the information content of a single photon for both of these cases. This enables simple calculation as to the expected precision using only the number of photons; as an example, with 10^5 photons the 3D orientation of a luminescent probe can be determined with 0.86° precision in θ and 0.15° precision in ϕ . For a scattering probe (here a $92\text{ nm} \times 40\text{ nm}$ Au rod), the 3D orientation can be determined with 1.3° precision in θ and 0.17° precision in ϕ using 10^5 photons. In Fig. 14, this single result is extended over a large range of photon numbers and signal-to-background ratios, and shows that luminescence generally gives a better 3D-orientation determination over scattering.

Practical considerations such as how the measurement uncertainty may be affected by scatterer shape (Fig. 12–13), experimental implementation (Fig. 7–10), and by signal strength (Fig. 3–5) are also discussed. In addition, the advantages of scatterers—that they can provide a considerably higher photon flux with respect to single chromophores, they do not bleach and nor do they blink—mean that for probing fast rotational dynamics they can be a better choice than a chromophore, despite in principle the measurement uncertainties being lower for luminescence experiments at the same number of photons and signal-to-background ratio. Overall, we provide both a guide to experimentalists in implementing new experiments as well as providing information limits as to what can be fundamentally known when measuring 3D orientation in a division-of-amplitude polarimetry experiment.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary functions for equations 3, 9, 11, 12. MLE for scattering and fluorescence experiments. Plot and equations describing the Cramér-Rao lower bounds as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$. Plots of how the Cramér-Rao lower bounds as a function of ϕ change as a function of detector alignment. Example plots for dependence of intensity on θ . Plot for how measurement uncertainty changes for changing NA, fluorescence case. Plots for how the change of detection wavelength changes the measurement uncertainty of measured orientation in the fluorescence experiment. Plots for changing R , ξ of rods and ellipsoids and the effect on orientation measurement uncertainty. A plot of the effect of detector misalignment on the fluorescence experiment.

The MAT3DOrient and Py3DOrient packages may be accessed via the Yang lab or through the repositories <https://github.com/PrincetonUniversity/MAT3DOrient> and <https://github.com/PrincetonUniversity/Py3DOrient>, respectively. All calculations presented here were run on MAT3DOrient. Unit testing shows all Fisher information matrices to give identical results (to within numerical error),

however it is possible due to different languages using different matrix inversion algorithms that inverting the matrix to get σ_{ij} values may yield minor differences.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project was supported by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation (#4741). JSB thanks the Fonds National Suisse de la Recherche Scientifique for financial support in the form of an Early Postdoc.Mobility grant (Project no. P2GEP2_191208). Dr. M. Junaid Amin and Dr. Nyssa T. Emerson are warmly thanked for valuable scientific discussions. Lastly, we thank the anonymous reviewers for constructive suggestions that brought the work to its present form.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

- ¹P. Siders, R. J. Cave, and R. A. Marcus, "A model for orientation effects in electron-transfer reactions," *J. Chem. Phys.* **81**, 5613–5624 (1984).
- ²B. Wu, M. Maroncelli, and E. W. Castner, "Photoinduced Bimolecular Electron Transfer in Ionic Liquids," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **139**, 14568–14585 (2017).
- ³M. Rini, B.-Z. Magnes, E. Pines, and E. T. J. Nibbering, "Real-Time Observation of Bimodal Proton Transfer in Acid-Base Pairs in Water," *Science* **301**, 349–352 (2003).
- ⁴M. Rini, D. Pines, B.-Z. Magnes, E. Pines, and E. T. J. Nibbering, "Bimodal proton transfer in acid-base reactions in water," *J. Chem. Phys.* **121**, 9593–9610 (2004).
- ⁵M. M. Sartin, K. Kondo, M. Yoshizawa, S. Takeuchi, and T. Tahara, "Local environment inside a novel aromatic micelle investigated by steady-state and femtosecond fluorescence spectroscopy of an encapsulated solvatochromic probe," *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **19**, 757–765 (2016).
- ⁶M. Molaei, E. Atefi, and J. C. Crocker, "Nanoscale Rheology and Anisotropic Diffusion Using Single Gold Nanorod Probes," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120**, 118002 (2018).
- ⁷M. M. Tirado and J. G. de la Torre, "Rotational dynamics of rigid, symmetric top macromolecules. Application to circular cylinders," *J. Chem. Phys.* **73**, 1986–1993 (1980).
- ⁸J. G. de la Torre and V. A. Bloomfield, "Hydrodynamic properties of complex, rigid, biological macromolecules: Theory and applications," *Quarterly Reviews of Biophysics* **14**, 81–139 (1981).
- ⁹J. T. Fourkas, "Rapid determination of the three-dimensional orientation of single molecules," *Opt. Lett.* **26**, 211–213 (2001).
- ¹⁰H. Yang, "Single-Particle Light Scattering: Imaging and Dynamical Fluctuations in the Polarization and Spectral Response," *J. Phys. Chem. A* **111**, 4987–4997 (2007).
- ¹¹J. Sepioł, J. Jasny, J. Keller, and U. P. Wild, "Single molecules observed by immersion mirror objective. The orientation of terrylene molecules via the direction of its transition dipole moment," *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **273**, 444–448 (1997).
- ¹²T. M. Cover and J. A. Thomas, *Elements of Information Theory*, 2nd ed. (Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, N.J., 2006).
- ¹³B. Sick, B. Hecht, and L. Novotny, "Orientational Imaging of Single Molecules by Annular Illumination," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **85**, 4482–4485 (2000).
- ¹⁴E. Toprak, J. Enderlein, S. Syed, S. A. McKinney, R. G. Petschek, T. Ha, Y. E. Goldman, and P. R. Selvin, "Defocused orientation and position imaging (DOPI) of myosin V," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **103**, 6495–6499 (2006).
- ¹⁵M. P. Backlund, M. D. Lew, A. S. Backer, S. J. Sahl, G. Grover, A. Agrawal, R. Piestun, and W. E. Moerner, "Simultaneous, accurate measurement of the 3D position and orientation of single molecules," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **109**, 19087–19092 (2012).
- ¹⁶A. S. Backer, M. Y. Lee, and W. E. Moerner, "Enhanced DNA imaging using super-resolution microscopy and simultaneous single-molecule orientation measurements," *Optica* **3**, 659–666 (2016).
- ¹⁷C. A. V. Cruz, H. A. Shaban, A. Kress, N. Bertaux, S. Monneret, M. Mavrikis, J. Savatier, and S. Brasselet, "Quantitative nanoscale imaging of orientational order in biological filaments by polarized superresolution microscopy," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **113**, E820–E828 (2016).
- ¹⁸J. Lu, H. Mazidi, T. Ding, O. Zhang, and M. D. Lew, "Single-Molecule 3D Orientation Imaging Reveals Nanoscale Compositional Heterogeneity in Lipid Membranes," *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **59**, 17572–17579 (2020).
- ¹⁹J. N. Forkey, M. E. Quinlan, and Y. E. Goldman, "Measurement of Single Macromolecule Orientation by Total Internal Reflection Fluorescence Polarization Microscopy," *Biophys. J.* **89**, 1261–1271 (2005).
- ²⁰J. F. Beausang, H. W. Schroeder, P. C. Nelson, and Y. E. Goldman, "Twirling of Actin by Myosins II and V Observed via Polarized TIRF in a Modified Gliding Assay," *Biophys. J.* **95**, 5820–5831 (2008).
- ²¹E. J. G. Peterman, H. Sosa, L. S. B. Goldstein, and W. E. Moerner, "Polarized Fluorescence Microscopy of Individual and Many Kinesin Motors Bound to Axonemal Microtubules," *Biophys. J.* **81**, 2851–2863 (2001).
- ²²M. Prummer, B. Sick, B. Hecht, and U. P. Wild, "Three-dimensional optical polarization tomography of single molecules," *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 9824–9829 (2003).
- ²³J. H. Lewis, J. F. Beausang, H. L. Sweeney, and Y. E. Goldman, "The azimuthal path of myosin V and its dependence on lever-arm length," *J. Gen. Physiol.* **139**, 101–120 (2012).
- ²⁴M. Ohmachi, Y. Komori, A. H. Iwane, F. Fujii, T. Jin, and T. Yanagida, "Fluorescence microscopy for simultaneous observation of 3D orientation and movement and its application to quantum rod-tagged myosin V," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **109**, 5294–5298 (2012).
- ²⁵L. G. Lippert, T. Dadosh, J. A. Hadden, V. Karnawat, B. T. Diroll, C. B. Murray, E. L. F. Holzbaur, K. Schulten, S. L. Reck-Peterson, and Y. E. Goldman, "Angular measurements of the dynein ring reveal a stepping mechanism dependent on a flexible stalk," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **114**, E4564–E4573 (2017).
- ²⁶M. R. Foreman and P. Török, "Fundamental limits in single-molecule orientation measurements," *New J. Phys.* **13**, 093013 (2011).
- ²⁷O. Zhang and M. D. Lew, "Quantum limits for precisely estimating the orientation and wobble of dipole emitters," *Phys. Rev. Research* **2**, 033114 (2020).
- ²⁸O. Zhang and M. D. Lew, "Single-molecule orientation localization microscopy I: Fundamental limits," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **38**, 277–287 (2021).
- ²⁹O. Zhang and M. D. Lew, "Single-molecule orientation localization microscopy II: A performance comparison," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **38**, 288–297 (2021).
- ³⁰I. H. El-Sayed, X. Huang, and M. A. El-Sayed, "Surface Plasmon Resonance Scattering and Absorption of anti-EGFR Antibody Conjugated Gold Nanoparticles in Cancer Diagnostics: Applications in Oral Cancer," *Nano Lett.* **5**, 829–834 (2005).
- ³¹X. Huang, I. H. El-Sayed, W. Qian, and M. A. El-Sayed, "Cancer Cell Imaging and Photothermal Therapy in the Near-Infrared Region by Using Gold Nanorods," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **128**, 2115–2120 (2006).
- ³²J. Yguerabide and E. E. Yguerabide, "Light-Scattering Submicroscopic Particles as Highly Fluorescent Analogs and Their Use as Tracer Labels in Clinical and Biological Applications: II. Experimental Characterization," *Anal. Biochem.* **262**, 157–176 (1998).
- ³³R. Yasuda, H. Noji, M. Yoshida, K. Kinoshita, and H. Itoh, "Resolution of distinct rotational substeps by submillisecond kinetic analysis of F1-ATPase," *Nature* **410**, 898–904 (2001).
- ³⁴M. Mazaheri, J. Ehrig, A. Shkarin, V. Ziburdaev, and V. Sandoghdar, "Ultrahigh-Speed Imaging of Rotational Diffusion on a Lipid Bilayer," *Nano Lett.* **20**, 7213–7219 (2020).
- ³⁵S. Link, M. B. Mohamed, and M. A. El-Sayed, "Simulation of the Optical Absorption Spectra of Gold Nanorods as a Function of Their Aspect Ratio and the Effect of the Medium Dielectric Constant," *J. Phys. Chem. B* **103**, 3073–3077 (1999).
- ³⁶R. Yu, L. M. Liz-Marzán, and F. J. G. de Abajo, "Universal analytical modeling of plasmonic nanoparticles," *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **46**, 6710–6724 (2017).

- ³⁷L. F. Guerra, T. W. Muir, and H. Yang, "Single-Particle Dynamic Light Scattering: Shapes of Individual Nanoparticles," *Nano Lett.* **19**, 5530–5536 (2019).
- ³⁸H. Cang, C. M. Wong, C. S. Xu, A. H. Rizvi, and H. Yang, "Confocal three dimensional tracking of a single nanoparticle with concurrent spectroscopic readouts," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **88**, 223901 (2006).
- ³⁹L. P. Watkins and H. Yang, "Information Bounds and Optimal Analysis of Dynamic Single Molecule Measurements," *Biophys. J.* **86**, 4015–4029 (2004).
- ⁴⁰K. Adachi, R. Yasuda, H. Noji, H. Itoh, Y. Harada, M. Yoshida, and K. Kinoshita, "Stepping rotation of F1-ATPase visualized through angle-resolved single-fluorophore imaging," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **97**, 7243–7247 (2000).
- ⁴¹S. Deka, A. Quarta, M. G. Lupo, A. Falqui, S. Boninelli, C. Gianini, G. Morello, M. De Giorgi, G. Lanzani, C. Spinella, R. Cingolani, T. Pellegrino, and L. Manna, "CdSe/CdS/ZnS Double Shell Nanorods with High Photoluminescence Efficiency and Their Exploitation As Biolabeling Probes," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **131**, 2948–2958 (2009).
- ⁴²J. Hu, L.-s. Li, W. Yang, L. Manna, L.-w. Wang, and A. P. Alivisatos, "Linearly Polarized Emission from Colloidal Semiconductor Quantum Rods," *Science* **292**, 2060–2063 (2001).
- ⁴³A. H. Harvey, J. S. Gallagher, and J. M. H. L. Sengers, "Revised Formulation for the Refractive Index of Water and Steam as a Function of Wavelength, Temperature and Density," *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* **IWPS2019**, 761–774 (1998).
- ⁴⁴S. Ram, E. S. Ward, and R. J. Ober, "How accurately can a single molecule be localized in three dimensions using a fluorescence microscope?" in *Imaging, Manipulation, and Analysis of Biomolecules and Cells: Fundamentals and Applications III*, Vol. 5699 (International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2005) pp. 426–435.
- ⁴⁵R. J. Ober, S. Ram, and E. S. Ward, "Localization Accuracy in Single-Molecule Microscopy," *Biophysical Journal* **86**, 1185–1200 (2004).
- ⁴⁶R. Gans, "über die Form ultramikroskopischer Goldteilchen," *Ann. Phys. (Berl.)* **342**, 881–900 (1912).
- ⁴⁷D. Y. Shroder, L. G. Lippert, and Y. E. Goldman, "Single molecule optical measurements of orientation and rotations of biological macromolecules," *Methods Appl. Fluoresc.* **4**, 042004 (2016).
- ⁴⁸F. Sturzenegger, F. Zosel, E. D. Holmstrom, K. J. Buholzer, D. E. Makarov, D. Nettels, and B. Schuler, "Transition path times of coupled folding and binding reveal the formation of an encounter complex," *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 4708 (2018).
- ⁴⁹Q. Wang and W. E. Moerner, "Single-molecule motions enable direct visualization of biomolecular interactions in solution," *Nat. Methods* **11**, 555–558 (2014).
- ⁵⁰W. E. Moerner and D. P. Fromm, "Methods of single-molecule fluorescence spectroscopy and microscopy," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **74**, 3597–3619 (2003).
- ⁵¹M. Rafipoor, C. Schmidtke, C. Wolter, C. Strelow, H. Weller, and H. Lange, "Clustering of CdSe/CdS Quantum Dot/Quantum Rods into Micelles Can Form Bright, Non-blinking, Stable, and Biocompatible Probes," *Langmuir* **31**, 9441–9447 (2015).